

Theoretical evaluation of viscosity in binary solutions of acetophenone at 308.15 K

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Abstract : Viscosities of four binary liquid mixtures : acetophenone-tetrahydrofuran (THF), acetophenone-hexane, acetophenone-dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetophenone-methanol in different compositions have been measured and compared with theoretical values calculated by using various empirical relations. In some cases, fairly good agreement between experimental and theoretical values, calculated by different theories is observed in all the four systems. Further, an attempt has been made to study the intermolecular interactions in the four systems at 308.15 K, in terms of excess free energy of mixing, strength of interaction parameters and interaction energy. It is observed that interactions can be estimated in binary systems both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Keywords : Binary liquid mixtures, viscosity, intermolecular interaction, acetophenone.

Thermodynamic properties of solutions have proven to be a very useful tool in elucidating the structural interactions among components. Further, viscosities of liquid mixtures are of interest to chemical industry and chemical engineering. Few workers have reported theoretical viscosities in binary¹ and ternary liquid mixtures². In continuation with our earlier work³, viscosities and densities are measured for various compositions of four binary liquid systems : acetophenone-tetrahydrofuran (ACE-THF), acetophenone-hexane (ACE-HX), acetophenone-dimethylformamide (ACE-DMF) and acetophenone-methanol (ACE-MH). The experimental results are compared with theoretical values calculated from various viscosity theories and are interpreted in terms of structure of molecules of components and the interactions involved. Some thermodynamics parameters such as strength of interaction parameters (d), interaction energy (W_{vis}) and excess free energy of mixing (αF_m) have also been evaluated⁴ to provide additional information on molecular interactions.

Experimental

The liquids used in the present study were purified by standard method⁵. All the mixtures of different compositions were prepared by volume and were kept in stoppered bottles to minimize the error due to evaporation. The densities and viscosities all the solutions were measured by specific gravity bottle and Ubbelohde viscometer at 308.15 K.

Theory :

For binary liquid mixtures, Bingham proposed⁶ the following relation, which gives ideal viscosity of the mixture :

$$\eta = \sum x_i \eta_i \quad (1)$$

where x_i and η_i are the mole fraction and viscosity of the i -th component respectively.

Additive relation based on Arrhenius and Eyring's model⁷ for the viscosity of pure liquids can be modified as :

$$\ln \eta V = \sum x_i \ln \eta_i V_i \quad (2)$$

where V_i is the volume of the i -th component.

Kendall and Munroe⁸ gave the following equation for multi component systems;

$$\ln \eta = \sum x_i \ln \eta_i \quad (3)$$

The Katti and Chaudhari relation⁹ is modified for binary liquid system and is given by :

$$\ln \eta V = \sum x_i \ln \eta_i V_i + (W_{vis}/RT)X_1X_2 \quad (4)$$

where W_{vis} is the interaction energy parameter and is given by :

$$W_{vis} = (RT/X_1X_2) \ln (V/\sum V_i x_i) + dRT \quad (5)$$

where V is the volume of the mixture and d is the Grunberg-Nissam interaction parameter which is given

by :

$$d = -(\alpha F_m / X_1 X_2 RT) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \alpha F_m = -RT(\ln \eta_{\text{exp}} - \ln \eta_{\text{Bring}}) \quad (7)$$

where η_{exp} is the experimental viscosity and η_{Bring} is the viscosity calculated by eq. (1).

The Grunberg and Nissam relation¹⁰ for the viscosity of non-ideal mixture is given by :

$$\ln \eta = \sum x_i \ln \eta_i + X_1 X_2 d \quad (8)$$

Results and discussion

From the above equations, the theoretical values of viscosities and thermodynamic parameters like excess free energy of mixing, strength of interaction parameter and interaction energy etc. are calculated for all the systems

and are given in Table 1 along with experimental values of viscosities.

It is evident from Table 1 that for ACE + THF system, Bingham relation gives better results in comparison to other theories where differences are higher between experimental and theoretical values. In ACE + HX system, Kendall and Arrhenius relations give better results. However, values calculated by Bingham, Grunberg and Nissam¹⁰ and Katti and Chaudhari relations are higher than those observed experimentally. For ACE + DMF system, experimental and theoretical values are very close except in some compositions. In ACE + MH system, Grunberg and Nissam relation gives values close to experimental values, followed by Bingham relation (except at higher X_{ACE}). Whereas values calculated by other theo-

Table 1. Values of thermodynamic parameters and experimental and theoretical viscosities for the four systems

X_{ACE}	η_{exp}	η_{Bring}	η_{Ken}	η_{GN}	η_{KC}	η_{Arr}	d	αF_m	W_{vis}
Acetophenone + THF									
0.1182	0.0045	0.0048	0.0044	0.0041	0.0046	0.0043	-0.5411	144.5031	1478.9859
0.2149	0.0051	0.0055	0.0049	0.0045	0.0053	0.0048	-0.5290	228.6520	1332.0993
0.3194	0.0058	0.0064	0.0055	0.0050	0.0059	0.0054	-0.4455	248.0981	1093.1066
0.4131	0.0071	0.0071	0.0061	0.0061	0.0060	0.0061	-0.0030	1.8605	-103.1039
0.5135	0.0076	0.0079	0.0068	0.0065	0.0070	0.0068	-0.1685	107.8436	340.6780
0.6215	0.0095	0.0088	0.0077	0.0083	0.0071	0.0076	0.3097	-186.6494	-772.8267
0.7139	0.0097	0.0095	0.0086	0.0087	0.0083	0.0085	0.1067	-55.8426	-298.2525
0.8122	0.0100	0.0103	0.0096	0.0093	0.0097	0.0095	-0.1882	73.5559	454.2022
0.9169	0.0111	0.0111	0.0108	0.0107	0.0107	0.0107	-0.0495	9.6647	86.7208
Acetophenone + Hexane									
0.1101	0.0031	0.0036	0.0030	0.0026	0.0035	0.0030	-1.5136	379.9389	4155.0794
0.2178	0.0035	0.0046	0.0036	0.0027	0.0047	0.0035	-1.6364	714.2183	4224.0627
0.3231	0.0040	0.0055	0.0042	0.0030	0.0058	0.0042	-1.5087	845.3498	3904.9507
0.4261	0.0046	0.0065	0.0049	0.0034	0.0070	0.0049	-1.4519	909.6370	3703.5633
0.5069	0.0056	0.0072	0.0055	0.0043	0.0071	0.0055	-0.9989	639.6511	2548.8802
0.6060	0.0066	0.0082	0.0065	0.0052	0.0080	0.0065	-0.8839	540.6789	2216.8216
0.7030	0.0072	0.0091	0.0075	0.0060	0.0094	0.0074	-1.0922	584.2564	2995.4077
0.8167	0.0093	0.0101	0.0089	0.0082	0.0097	0.0090	-0.5762	220.9898	1389.2121
0.9093	0.0112	0.0110	0.0103	0.0105	0.0101	0.0103	0.2218	-46.8673	-739.1432
Acetophenone + DMF									
0.1116	0.0070	0.0069	0.0067	0.0068	0.0065	0.0066	0.1811	-46.0127	-384.9332
0.2011	0.0078	0.0074	0.0071	0.0075	0.0067	0.0070	0.3105	-127.7857	-795.6758
0.3054	0.0089	0.0080	0.0076	0.0085	0.0067	0.0075	0.5242	-284.8825	-1342.3342
0.4167	0.0085	0.0086	0.0082	0.0081	0.0081	0.0080	-0.0377	23.4779	130.3174
0.4973	0.0089	0.0090	0.0086	0.0084	0.0086	0.0084	-0.0755	48.3831	248.6311
0.6061	0.0096	0.0096	0.0092	0.0092	0.0090	0.0090	-0.0061	3.7564	98.1251
0.7001	0.0102	0.0101	0.0098	0.0098	0.0096	0.0096	0.0194	-10.4413	-55.8092
0.8020	0.0107	0.0107	0.0104	0.0104	0.0103	0.0103	0.0180	-7.3109	-75.4551
0.9118	0.0111	0.0113	0.0112	0.0109	0.0113	0.0111	-0.2605	53.6655	639.5144

Acetophenone + Methanol									
0.0982	0.0056	0.0056	0.0054	0.0053	0.0051	0.0050	-0.0762	17.2769	104.8443
0.1997	0.0067	0.0063	0.0059	0.0063	0.0049	0.0053	0.4149	-169.8883	-1141.1133
0.3049	0.0076	0.0070	0.0064	0.0070	0.0052	0.0057	0.3868	-210.0403	-1156.1204
0.4009	0.0083	0.0077	0.0070	0.0075	0.0057	0.0062	0.2995	-184.2895	-892.0161
0.4952	0.0092	0.0083	0.0076	0.0084	0.0060	0.0067	0.3786	-242.4832	-1064.6739
0.6110	0.0102	0.0091	0.0084	0.0094	0.0067	0.0075	0.4525	-275.5559	-1241.8282
0.7165	0.0107	0.0099	0.0092	0.0100	0.0077	0.0084	0.4056	-211.0997	-1073.6562
0.7986	0.0141	0.0104	0.0099	0.0134	0.0068	0.0092	1.8798	-774.5778	-4868.4624
0.8922	0.0153	0.0111	0.0107	0.0148	0.0075	0.0103	3.3499	-825.4497	-8598.1991

ries differ much in comparison to experimental values.

These differences between experimental and theoretical viscosity values are also reported in terms of percentage deviations given in Table 2. It is observed that for ACE + THF system, deviations between experimental and theoretical values are higher except for those calculated by Bingham relation. In ACE + HX system, good agreement between experimental and theoretical values calculated by Kendall and Arrhenius relations are observed. However, deviations are higher for those calculated by Bingham, Grunberg and Nissam and Katti and Chaudhari relations. For ACE + DMF system, good

agreement is observed between experimental and theoretical values calculated by all the theories except in some compositions. In ACE + MH system, better agreement is observed with Grunberg and Nissam relation, followed by Bingham relation (except at higher X_{ACE}). Higher deviations are observed for the values calculated by other theories.

The Arrhenius relation is based on additive property which is for ideal systems where there is no interaction between molecules. Thus, it gives satisfactory results for ACE + HX system followed by ACE + DMF and ACE + THF systems. This indicates that in ACE + HX, in-

Table 2. Deviation between experimental and theoretical values of viscosity in the four systems

X_{ACE}	$\Delta\eta_{exp}-\eta_{Bing}$ (%)	$\Delta\eta_{exp}-\eta_{Ken}$ (%)	$\Delta\eta_{exp}-\eta_{GN}$ (%)	$\Delta\eta_{exp}-\eta_{KC}$ (%)	$\Delta\eta_{exp}-\eta_{Arr}$ (%)
Acetophenone + THF					
0.1182	-6.67	2.22	8.89	-2.22	4.44
0.2149	-7.84	3.92	11.76	-3.92	5.88
0.3194	-10.34	5.17	13.79	-1.72	6.90
0.4131	0.00	14.08	14.08	15.49	14.08
0.5135	-3.95	10.53	14.47	7.89	10.53
0.6215	7.37	18.95	12.63	25.26	20.00
0.7139	2.06	11.34	10.31	14.43	12.37
0.8122	-3.00	4.00	7.00	3.00	5.00
0.9169	0.00	2.70	3.60	3.60	3.60
Acetophenone + Hexane					
0.1101	-16.13	3.23	16.13	-12.90	3.23
0.2178	-31.43	-2.86	22.86	-34.29	0.00
0.3231	-37.50	-5.00	25.00	-45.00	-5.00
0.4261	-41.30	-6.52	26.09	-52.17	-6.52
0.5069	-28.57	1.79	23.21	-26.79	1.79
0.6060	-24.24	1.52	21.21	-21.21	1.52
0.7030	-26.39	-4.17	16.67	-30.56	-2.78
0.8167	-8.60	4.30	11.83	-4.30	3.23
0.9093	1.79	8.04	6.25	9.82	8.04

Acetophenone + DMF					
0.1116	1.43	4.29	2.86	7.14	5.71
0.2011	5.13	8.97	3.85	14.10	10.26
0.3054	10.11	14.61	4.49	24.72	15.73
0.4167	-1.18	3.53	4.71	4.71	5.88
0.4973	-1.12	3.37	5.62	3.37	5.62
0.6061	0.00	4.17	4.17	6.25	6.25
0.7001	0.98	3.92	3.92	5.88	5.88
0.8020	0.00	2.80	2.80	3.74	3.74
0.9118	-1.80	-0.90	1.80	-1.80	0.00
Acetophenone + Methanol					
0.0982	0.00	3.57	5.36	8.93	10.71
0.1997	5.97	11.94	5.97	26.87	20.90
0.3049	7.89	15.79	7.89	31.58	25.00
0.4009	7.23	15.66	9.64	31.33	25.30
0.4952	9.78	17.39	8.70	34.78	27.17
0.6110	10.78	17.65	7.84	34.31	26.47
0.7165	7.48	14.02	6.54	28.04	21.50
0.7986	26.24	29.79	4.96	51.77	34.75
0.8922	27.45	30.07	3.27	50.98	32.68

teractions are minimum. In THF and DMF systems also, interactions are minimum except in some compositions. In THF, for intermediate X_{ACE} range, interactions are higher whereas in DMF system, at lower X_{ACE} range, interactions predominate. For ACE + MH system, the deviations are much higher suggesting thereby strong interactions between molecules of the component as expected due to hydrogen bonding.

The quantitative estimation of interactions in a mixture can be done by the strength of interaction parameter d . Table 1 shows that d values are both positive and negative. In ACE + HX, it is negative for all X_{ACE} except at $X_{ACE} = 0.9093$. For ACE + THF also, it is negative for all whereas for ACE + DMF, only for some compositions, the values are negative. For ACE + MH system, except at $X_{ACE} = 0.0982$, all d values are positive. When d values are greater than zero, strong interactions are present whereas less than zero values suggest the presence of weak interactions in a system¹¹. Thus, this again proves that in ACE + MH system, strong interactions are present whereas in ACE + HX, minimum interactions exist.

αF_m is also a measure of excess free energy of mixing. The values of αF_m are both positive and negative (Table 1). For ACE + THF system, values are positive for all except for some intermediate composition, where

the values are negative. For ACE + HX system, the values are positive for all compositions except at $X_{ACE} = 0.9093$. For ACE + DMF, it is both positive and negative whereas for ACE + HX system, it is negative for all except at one lower X_{ACE} . A negative value suggests strong interaction whereas positive value is indication of weak interaction. Thus, this again proves the existence of strong interactions in methanol system and minimum interactions in hexane system. This is further supported by interaction energy (W_{vis}), which is negative for methanol and positive for hexane system except at higher X_{ACE} . In other two systems, ACE + THF and ACE + DMF, these values are both positive and negative.

It is concluded that the studied theories can be applied to binary systems. However, some modifications should be done to improve the deviations in systems where interactions are stronger.

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